

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

Deliverable: D6.2 Core services Release #1

14/09/2020

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Core services Release #1 Core services Release #1

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NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the list of the core services released by NEANIAS project in its first release cycle, due in M10 of the project.

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1. Short deliverable report

1.1. Context

The deliverable D6.2 “Core services Release #1” is produced in the context of WP6 “Core Services Foundation and Implementation” of NEANIAS project. Services released are further detailed in deliverable D7.1 [1].

The deliverable refers to services released under the group of Core services that enable NEANIAS infrastructure manifestation, Open Science onboarding and generic visualization and Artificial Intelligence technologies exploitation.

This document serves as a short reference to the respective digital artifacts (as the deliverable is of type “OTHER”), presenting a brief enumeration of the services delivered, located in the next subsection 1.2 “Table of Services”.

1.2. Table of Services

The following table presents the services released in this 1st cycle.

Table 1 – Services and software released

Short name	Sector ¹	Lead ²	TRL ³	Version ⁴	Core Integration ⁵	Documentation Status ⁶	Testing Status ⁷	EOSC Registration Status ⁸
Zenodo	C1	NKUA	TRL9		n/a	Complete	Complete	n/a
DVS	C1	NKUA	TRL6	1.0.0	AAI	Draft	In progress	no
Catalogue Service	C1	ATHENA	TRL6	1.0rc	AAI	Draft	In progress	no
NENIAS AAI	C2	CITE	TRL7	1.1.0	None	Complete	Complete	n/a
Configuration Service	C2	CITE	TRL7	1.0.0	None	Complete	In progress	n/a
Service Instance Registry	C2	CITE	TRL6	1.0.0	None	Complete	In progress	n/a
Logging	C2	CITE	TRL7	1.0.0	None	Complete	In progress	n/a
Notifications	C2	CITE	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	Complete	In progress	n/a
Data Transfer	C2	SZTAKI	TRL6	1.0.0	None	Complete	N/A	no

¹ C1/C2/C3/C4/S1/S2/S3/U1/U2/U3/A1/A2/A3

² Organisation leading implementation

³ TRL level at release. All services start from TRL6.

⁴ Version according to service issuer

⁵ Integration level w.r.t. core NEANIAS services (AAI, Accounting, Monitoring, FAIRness support ...)

⁶ Level of documentation status: draft, under-update, complete, validated

⁷ Testing status: mention the status w.r.t. unit, integration, user acceptance testing (N/A, in progress, complete, failed)

⁸ Is service listed in Neanias and EOSC catalogue? (yes, in progress, no, n/a)

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MiCADO	C2	SZTAKI	TRL6	1.0.0	None	Complete	N/A	no
Data Exploration	C2	MEEO	TRL8	1.0.0	AAI	Complete	Complete	no
C3.1-AI-Gateway	C3	SZTAKI	TRL6	1.0.0	AAI	Draft	N/A	no
C3.2-Model-Serving	C3	ALTEC	TRL6	1.0.0	None	Draft	N/A	no
C3.3-Horovod-Cluster	C3	SZTAKI	TRL6	1.0.0	None	Draft	N/A	no
C3.4-Spark-Cluster	C3	UNIMIB	TRL6	1.0.0	None	Draft	N/A	no
C4.1- Visual Discovery Framework	C4	INAF/UoP/CORONIS	TRL6	1.0.0	None	Complete	In progress	no
C4.2- Visualization Gateway	C4	INAF	TRL6	1.0.0	AAI	Draft	N/A	no
C4.3- Toolkit for Cross Realities	C4	ALTEC	TRL6	1.0.0	None	Complete	In progress	no
C4.4-Spatial Data Stores	C4	JACOBS	TRL6	1.0.0	AAI	Draft	Complete	n/a

1.3. Further information

All services of the release are available under the development infrastructure.

Depending on service provisioning model, the services may be already available or await for WP7 deployment tasks for their broader availability.

The next full release cycle is planned for M21 of the project, yet several interim releases of services will be scheduled by their respective owners and implementers.

The details about the Core services architecture can be found in D6.1 "Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications".

The details about the services released can be found in D6.3 "Core services software release report #1".

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References

- [1] NEANIAS collaboration, "D6.1 - Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications," 2020.